

Exploring Perceptions of University Students on Healthy and Unhealthy Eating: A Qualitative Study on Fruits, Vegetables, and Fast Food Consumption

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Abstract

University students are at a critical life stage where they gain autonomy over their food choices, which often results in significant changes to dietary habits and may influence long-term health outcomes, including the risk of developing chronic diseases. This study explored the perceptions of healthy and unhealthy eating among undergraduate students at Horizon Campus, Sri Lanka, focusing on fast food, fruits, and vegetable consumption. A qualitative, exploratory approach was used, and twelve students representing all seven faculties participated in face-to-face, semi-structured interviews lasting 20–30 minutes. Data was analyzed manually using thematic content analysis, and responses were grouped into six major themes: general eating habits, perceptions of healthy eating, fast food consumption, fruits and vegetables consumption, behavioral drivers, and attitudes and challenges. The analysis revealed that while students demonstrated a clear understanding of healthy eating, including the importance of balanced meals and nutrient-rich fruits and vegetables, their food choices were predominantly influenced by convenience, affordability, and peer behavior. Fast food was the preferred choice during busy academic schedules, despite awareness of its negative health effects such as gastritis and weight gain. Fruits and vegetables were recognized as essential for good health but consumed irregularly due to higher cost, limited availability on campus, and time constraints. The findings highlight a gap between students' nutritional knowledge and their actual dietary practices. It is recommended that Horizon Campus introduce affordable healthy options, organize nutrition awareness programs, and improve the availability of fresh produce to promote sustainable healthy eating habits among students.

Keywords: *Healthy eating, University students, Fast food consumption, Fruits and vegetables, Qualitative study.*